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SICILIAN NATURALISTIC NEWS:

26 *Myrmecophilus fuscus*; 27 *Euzophera lunulella*; 28 *Andrena pellucens*;
29 *Xanthogramma dives*; 30 *Tachydromia arrogans*; 31 *Empis genualis*;
32 *Stichopogon elegantulus*; 33 *Melinda gentilis*; 34 *Ensina sochi*

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Key words: Orthoptera Myrmecophilidae; Lepidoptera Pyralidae; Hymenoptera Andrenidae; Diptera Syrphidae; Diptera Hybotidae; Diptera Empididae; Diptera Asilidae; Diptera Calliphoridae; Diptera Tephritidae, new records.

26) *Myrmecophilus (Myrmecophilus) fuscus* (Stalling, 2013) (Orthoptera Myrmecophilidae)

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area.

Source: author

Number of individuals: 1 (collection of Louis F. Cassar, Malta)

Site location: Bosco di Scorace (Trapani)

Date of observation: 4.IX.2022

Record validated by Louis F. Cassar & Thomas Stalling

Reasons of interest: The species had only been previously reported once

from eastern Sicily. This is the second record for Italy and Sicily (STALLING *et al.*, 2021)

References: STALLING, T., GJELDUM, A., MILAT, T. & PAVLOVI, M., 2021. *Myrmecophilus fuscus* Stalling, 2013 new for the fauna of Croatia (Orthoptera: Myrmecophilidae). *Nat. Croat.*, 30: 257–261.

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Fig. 1 — Female of *Myrmecophilus fuscus* (Photo by T. Stalling)

27) *Euzophera lunulella* (Costa, 1836) (Lepidoptera Pyralidae)

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area.

Source: author

Number of individuals: 1 male (collection of Lucio Morin)

Site location: Capo Granitola – Campobello di Mazara (Trapani)

Date of observation: 2.VII.2022

Record validated by Lucio Morin

Reasons of interest: The species has not been previously reported from Sicily. This is the first record (LERAUT, 2014).

References: LERAUT P., 2014. Moths of Europe. Vol. IV Pyralids 2. *N.A.P. Editions*. Verrières-le Buisson, 440 pp.

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Fig. 2 — Male of *Euzophera lunulella* (Photo by L. Morin)

28) *Andrena (Margandrena) pellucens* (Pérez, 1895) (Hymenoptera Andrenidae)

Source: <http://www.entomologiitaliani.net/public/forum/phpBB3/viewtopic.php?f=11&t=105666>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/hymenopteristsforum08/permalink/-3283937691740068/>

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area.

Number of individuals: 1 female (coll. Angelo Ditta)

Site location: RNI Lago Preola e Gorghi Tondi, Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 15.XI.2023

Record validated by Marco Selis & Jordi Compte Figueras

Reasons of interest: Previously in Sicily the species had only been reported from Santa Venerina (Catania) in 1949 by Arcidiacono, from mouth of the river Simeto, in 1989 by V. Nobile and in loc. Petulenti, Paternò (Catania), in 1999 by S. Tomarchio (NOBILE *et al.*, 2005). It's the fourth record in Sicily and

the first in western Sicily. The species is classified as Data Deficient according to IUCN (ROBERT, 2014).

References. ROBERTS S., 2014. *Andrena pellucens*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2014: e.T19199351A19201445; <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2014-3.RLTS.T19199351A19201445.en> (accessed on 25 September 2024). NOBILE V., MELONI C. & TOMARCHIO S., 2005. *Andrena* nuove per la Sicilia e la Sardegna (Hymenoptera, Andrenidae). I. *Boll. Soc. entomol. ital.*, 137 (3): 223-228.

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Fig. 3 — Female of *Andrena (Margandrena) pellucens* (Photo by A. Ditta)

29) *Xanthogramma dives* (Rondani, 1857) (Diptera Syrphidae)

Source: Ditteri italiani. <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/4VFEJr2bfxa9SVUn/>

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area.

Number of individuals: 1 male (Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht)

Site location: RNI Lago Preola e Gorgi Tondi, Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 4.X.2023

Record validated by Paul L.T. Beuk

Reasons of interest: The species has not been previously reported from Sicily (STEENIS *et al.*, 2014; NEDELJKOVIC *et al.*, 2018). This is the first record.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>;

<https://www.eu-nomen.eu/portal/taxon.php?GUID=urn:lsid:faunaeur.org:taxname:66089>

References: NEDELJKOVIC Z., RICARTE A., ŠAŠIC ZORIC L., AN M., OBREHT VIDA KOVIC D., & VUJIC A., 2018. The genus *Xanthogramma* Schiner, 1861 2 (Diptera: Syrphidae) in southeastern Europe. *Can. Entomol.*, 150(4): 440-464. STEENIS W., VAN BOT S., & BARENDREGT A., 2014. Twee nieuwe citroenzweefvliegen voor Nederland: *Xanthogramma dives* en *X. stackelbergi* (Diptera: Syrphidae). *Ned. Faun. Meded.*, 43: 27-35.

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Fig. 4 — Male of *Xanthogramma dives* (Photo by A. Ditta)

30) *Tachydromia arrogans* (Strobl, 1893) (Diptera Hybotidae)

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area.

Source: author

Number of individuals: 2 females (Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht)

Site location: RNI Lago Preola e Gorghi Tondi, Mazara del Vallo (Trapani); Monte Krono, Sciacca (Agrigento)

Date of observation: 24.III.2023 (the first) and 10.IV.2023 (the second)

Record validated by Paul L.T. Beuk

Reasons of interest: The species was previously reported from Sicily once in Monreale (Palermo) by Zerny (2 males and 1 female) in 1921 (CHVÁLA, 1969). This is the second record in Sicily after more than 100 years.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>;

<https://www.eu-nomen.eu/portal/taxon.php?GUID=urn:lsid:faunaeur.org:taxname:138287>

References: CHVÁLA M., 1969. Revision of Palaearctic species of the genus *Tachydromia* Meig. (= *Tachista* Loew) (Diptera, Empididae). *Acta Entomol. Mus. Natl. Pragae* 38: 415-524

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Fig. 5 — Female of *Tachydromia arrogans* (Photo by A. Ditta)

31) *Empis genualis* (Strobl, 1893) (Diptera Empididae)

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area.

Source: author

Number of individuals: 2 males, 1 female (Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht)

Site location: Contrada Roccazzo, Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 24.IV.2023

Record validated by Paul L.T. Beuk

Reasons of interest: The species has not been previously reported from Sicily (SYROVÁTKA, 2000). This is the first record.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>;
<https://www.eu-nomen.eu/portal/taxon.php?GUID=urn:lsid:faunaeur.org:taxname:136918>

Reference: SYROVÁTKA, O., 2000. Revision of G. Strobl's types of *Empis* s.str. species (Diptera, Empididae). Part II. *Acta Univers. Carol. Biol.*, 44: 195-236

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Fig. 6 — *Empis genualis* (Photo by A. Ditta)

32) *Stichopogon (Stichopogon) elegantulus* (Wiedemann in Meigen, 1820)
(Diptera Asilidae)

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area.

Source: author

Number of individuals: 1 female (Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht)

Site location: RNI Lago Preola e Gorghi Tondi, Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 5.VI.2022

Record validated by Paul L.T. Beuk

Reasons of interest: The species has not been previously reported from Sicily. This is the first record.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>;

<https://www.eu-nomen.eu/portal/taxon.php?GUID=urn:lsid:faunaeur.org:taxname:59949>

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Fig. 7 — Female of *Stichopogon (Stichopogon) elegantulus* (Photo by A. Ditta)

33) *Melinda gentilis* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830) (Diptera Calliphoridae)

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area.

Source: author

Number of individuals: 1 male (Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht)

Site location: RNI Lago Preola e Gorghetti Tondi, Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 22.II.2023

Record validated by Paul L.T. Beuk

Reasons of interest: The species has not been previously reported from Sicily (ROGNES, 1991). This is the first record.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>;

<https://www.eu-nomen.eu/portal/taxon.php?GUID=urn:lsid:faunaeur.org:taxname:397114>

Reference: ROGNES, K., 1991. Blowflies (Diptera, Calliphoridae) of Fennoscandia and Denmark. *Fauna Entomol. Scand.* 24: 1-272.

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Fig. 8 — Male of *Melinda gentilis* (Photo by P.L.T. Beuk)

34) *Ensina sonchi* (Linnaeus, 1767) (Diptera Tephritidae)**Source:**

<https://www.facebook.com/share/p/rbAvnaZ9XarK7ABa/>;

<https://www.facebook.com/share/p/b3HgRD7R58mCShBg/>

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area.

Number of individuals: 1 female, 1 male (Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht)

Site location: RNI Lago Preola e Gorgi Tondi, Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 6.VI.2021 and 5.III.2022

Record validated by Paul L.T. Beuk

Reasons of interest: The species has been reported once from continental Italy and once from Sicily. This is the third report from Italy and the second from Sicily (KOÇAK & KEMAL, 2015).

Resource: <https://zoobank.org/References/E3DC8785-2E1D-420C-8886-1690F7F0B605>

Reference: KOÇAK A.Ö. & KEMAL M., 2015. Initial results of the Entomofauna of SW Asia, based upon the info-system of the Cesa (excl. Lepidoptera). *Priamus* (Suppl.) 35: 1-1185, 185 maps.

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Fig. 9 — *Ensina sonchi* (Photo by P.L.T. Beuk)